

PECULIARITIES OF FAZIL ISKANDER'S CREATIVITY THROUGH THE PRISM OF NATIONAL IDENTITY

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Abstract: This article examines the originality of Fazil Iskander's creativity, the themes of his works, as well as the characteristics of the concept of "national specificity".

Key words: literature, themes of works, national specifics, writer's worldview.

The problem of mentality, national character, moral worldview of the people has become the object of study of various sciences - psychology, literary criticism, history, cultural studies, ethnography, etc. In determining the essence of the very concept of mentality, its structural elements and reasons for its formation, some uncertainty remains. An artistic attempt to comprehend the mountainous Caucasian mentality was carried out by A.S. Pushkin in the poem "Prisoner of the Caucasus". This attempt was of a romantic nature. Russian poets and writers of the 19th century A.A. Shishkov, A.I. Polezhaev, A.A. Bestuzhev-Marlinsky, M.Yu. Lermontov, L.N. Tolstoy continued to expand and deepen his artistic exploration of the national character.

The national character of any people is genetically determined by a long evolutionary process. Features of the mental makeup, types of thinking are determined by historically established traditions, social environment and upbringing, as well as hereditary inclinations.

Of great interest is the process of development of languages, cultures, literatures, when one or another image from one national literature "wedges" into another, changing under the influence of the laws of a foreign language. This is how the dialogue of national cultural traditions takes place in the aesthetic field of literature.

The problem of creating a national character acquires particular relevance in Russian literature of the 19th century, in connection with the growing activity of national self-awareness. With the beginning of the 20th century, interest in the very concept of "national" has intensified. The largest Russian writers of the 19th century - F.M. Dostoevsky, I.S. Turgenev, I.A. Goncharov, L.N. Tolstoy and others reproduced the Russian national character with varying degrees of integrity in their stories and novels, thereby anticipating the artistic searches of the 20th century in this area. A surge of interest in the lives of representatives of

other ethnic groups and the desire to create a multinational and international picture of the world are characteristic of Soviet culture and literature. During this period of time, a new term “Russian-language literature” arose; Soviet literature began to have a nationally specific character. Writers appeared who thought in the coordinates of one national culture, but expressed thoughts in the language, in the speech forms of another national culture. This is B. Okudzhava, and E. Asadov, and R. Gamzatov, Ch. Aitmatov, and many others.

All these writers in their books spoke about themselves, about local not in their native Russian language, which was quite difficult, since ideas about the world, the nature of thinking of the national hero, the ways of feeling the world of representatives of one or another nationality had to be “translated” into the linguistic code of another culture.

Many significant features of Fazil Iskander’s national identity, reflected in his work, especially in the middle of the 20th century, were caused by the events that took place in Russia and Abkhazia, and left their mark on the writer’s childhood and youth memory.

Throughout his entire career, Fazil Iskander expresses his views and experiences related to the Abkhaz people and their historical destiny in works of art and journalism. Iskander’s perception of the Abkhaz national character is a unique approach to the depiction of the peasantry and the countryside, which manifests itself in the ambiguity of the specifics of the national character, combining wicked manifestations coupled with the features of the national ideal. The depiction of positive and negative features of reality is explained by the author’s fundamental commitment to the objectivity of the narrative.

And yet, when studying the artistic world of a writer, the main attention should be paid to identifying the national ideal. Iskander's artistic concept of the national ideal presupposes an almost obligatory relationship between the present and the past. Continuity of generations, respect for elders, observance of norms, customs, traditions, adherence to the values embedded in the human soul - all these are the ideals of the writer, which, one way or another, manifested themselves in his work.

National specificity, national identity, the formation of national character - all this is of great interest to historians, psychologists and literary scholars. In this work, an attempt was made to identify ways and means of embodying national identity in the work of the living classic Fazil Iskander.

The work of Fazil Iskander can be called a unique phenomenon - it represents a synthesis of two cultures - Russian and Abkhazian. The writer

writes exclusively in Russian and refers in his works to the traditions of Russian classical literature, and therefore he has the right to call himself a Russian writer. However, an important fact is that the setting of almost all of Fazil Iskander's works is Abkhazia. The author, who grew up on this land, perfectly understands Abkhaz life, knows the worldview of the people, the history of the country, he is familiar with the customs and traditions of the Abkhazians, which is expressed in his prose.

In the works of Fazil Iskander, a complex artistic world arises, the origins of which are connected with the traditions of Russian literature, and in Russian literature the writer acts as the creator of a special type of literary laughter, the root of which is the absolute acceptance of existence. The writer's artistic world - comical and ironic, sad and cheerful, colorful and sensually tangible - is fundamentally new for Russian and Abkhaz literature.

The humor of Fazil Iskander preserves the productive connections of laughter with fun, fertility, life, denial of death inherent in folk art, the unity of the affirming and denying principles with a predominance approver. Humor is associated with the idea of freedom to perceive life and individual responsibility for moral choices.

Explicit and hidden quotes, a humorous rethinking of everything that happens in the world, an ironic approach to classical subjects of folklore, to Abkhaz mythology, Russian and world literature, to history - all this allows Fazil Iskander to embrace the immensity, to expand the scale of what is depicted.

Humor is a way of restoring the lost unity of being, a synonym for truth. Laughter is universal: it embraces the whole world. The writer's inexhaustible source of comedy is life itself. Resolving the conflict with the power of laughter and restoring the continuity of life is the principle of its plot construction.

The themes of Fazil Iskander's work are complex and varied, but the moral and spiritual search for the human personality and its development always comes to the fore. The author pays great attention to the formation of the characters of the heroes, the customs and traditions of his homeland and his people, notes their attachment to the land, and, of course, does not ignore the political adversities through which he reveals the images of the heroes and the specifics of national characters.

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